

Bayesian trial design to identify a sensitive subpopulation in non-proportional hazard settings

Akiyoshi Nakakura^{1,2}

¹Center for Clinical and Translational Research, Kyushu University Hospital, Japan

²Kurume University Graduate School of Medicine, Kurume, Japan

Abstract

In molecular-targeted drug development, biomarkers are increasingly integrated into clinical trial design to enable personalized treatment evaluation. Identifying subpopulations that derive the greatest benefit from novel agents facilitates efficient development. Traditional Bayesian subgroup identification designs rely on hazard ratios and thus require the proportional hazards assumption. However, this assumption often fails for modern therapies such as immune checkpoint inhibitors and targeted agents, which exhibit delayed or time-varying effects.

To address this limitation, we extend Morita et al.'s Bayesian phase II trial framework by incorporating the restricted mean survival time (RMST) as the primary endpoint. RMST provides an interpretable measure of average survival up to a fixed time horizon and does not depend on the PH assumption. The proposed Bayesian RMST-based design allows flexible and reliable identification of biomarker-defined subgroups even under non-proportional hazard conditions. Through extensive simulation studies covering delayed and crossing-hazard scenarios, we demonstrate that the RMST-based approach offers superior robustness, stable operating characteristics, and broad applicability to contemporary oncology trials.

Key Words: Bayesian, clinical trial design, Restricted mean survival time, Non-proportional hazards, Subgroup identification

1. Introduction

The landscape of cancer clinical trials has changed dramatically with the advent of molecular-targeted therapies and immunotherapies. These treatments frequently induce time-varying effects, such as delayed responses or long-term survival plateaus, which violate the proportional hazards assumption commonly used in Cox regression [1]. When this assumption fails, the hazard ratio no longer represents a constant measure of relative risk, reducing both interpretability and statistical power [2]. Consequently, new analytic frameworks that remain valid under non-PH conditions are needed to ensure accurate assessment of treatment efficacy [3, 4].

In early-phase oncology trials, particularly phase II studies, the identification of treatment-sensitive subpopulations based on biomarkers is of strategic importance [5, 6, 7]. Recognizing which subgroup benefits from therapy allows phase III confirmatory trials to focus on those patients, leading to shorter timelines, smaller sample sizes, and greater likelihood of success. Bayesian subgroup identification designs have been developed to address this need, offering a probabilistic framework for sequential evaluation and adaptive decision-making. Morita et al. [8] proposed elegant Bayesian phase II designs using hazard ratios to identify effective subgroups, while Sugitani et al. [9] introduced sequential extensions to reduce required sample size.

However, these HR-based designs become unreliable when survival curves cross or when treatment effects emerge after a latency period—situations commonly observed in immunotherapy and

targeted therapy trials [10, 11]. In such settings, the use of restricted mean survival time (RMST) provides an attractive alternative because it captures the cumulative survival benefit over a pre-specified time horizon without relying on proportionality [12]. RMST is directly interpretable in clinical terms ('average months of survival gained') and offers robust inference across complex survival patterns [13, 14, 15].

Building on this motivation, we propose a Bayesian RMST-based subgroup identification design that retains the interpretability of Bayesian decision rules while enhancing robustness to non-PH violations. The proposed method flexibly characterizes subgroup-specific treatment effects, enabling reliable identification of biomarker-sensitive populations in modern oncology trials.

2. Methods

2.1. Trial Setting

We consider a randomized phase II trial comparing a new molecular-targeted agent plus best supportive care (BSC) against placebo plus BSC. The primary endpoint is progression-free survival (PFS), and patients are categorized into four biomarker expression subgroups (0, 1+, 2+, 3+), representing increasing molecular expression levels.

Two biological assumptions guide the design:

1. Monotonicity: treatment efficacy is non-decreasing with biomarker expression; and
2. Specificity: biomarker expression influences only the new treatment, not the control arm.

These assumptions reflect common biological expectations that higher expression corresponds to greater drug sensitivity and that the biomarker acts as a predictive rather than prognostic factor [16].

2.2. Bayesian Model Based on RMST Difference

In the original design of Morita et al., subgroup efficacy was assessed by the posterior distribution of subgroup-specific hazard ratios. In the proposed extension, we instead evaluate treatment benefit through the difference in RMST between experimental and control arms.

The RMST up to time τ is defined as

$$\text{RMST}(\tau) = \int_0^\tau S(t) dt,$$

where $S(t)$ denotes the survival function. Following the Bayesian nonparametric approach of Zhang & Yin [17], $S(t)$ is modeled using a Dirichlet process mixture, allowing flexible estimation of complex survival shapes. Numerical integration via the trapezoidal rule yields posterior samples of RMST for each subgroup.

Let $\Delta_g = \text{RMST}_{\text{treat},g} - \text{RMST}_{\text{control},g}$ denote the RMST difference in subgroup g . A subgroup is deemed effective if

$$P(\Delta_g > \eta | \text{data}) > \pi,$$

where η represents the clinically meaningful threshold (e.g., one-month RMST gain) and π denotes the posterior confidence level (e.g., 0.7). In the present simulations, we set $\tau = 30$ months, $\eta = 1.4$ months, and $\pi = 0.7$, corresponding approximately to an HR of 0.8 in a 30-month trial.

2.3. Sequential Identification Procedure

Subgroups are evaluated sequentially from the lowest biomarker expression upward. Once a subgroup meets the efficacy criterion, all higher-expression subgroups are automatically declared effective according to the monotonicity constraint. This sequential procedure limits unnecessary testing and preserves interpretability, as it mimics the practical logic of dose-response relationships in biomarker-driven development.

The sequential Bayesian rule also facilitates efficient computation, since posterior updating proceeds cumulatively across subgroups. The resulting design can be implemented adaptively, allowing early stopping for efficacy or futility when sufficient evidence accrues.

3. Simulation Study

3.1. Simulation settings

A comprehensive simulation study was conducted to evaluate the operating characteristics of the proposed Bayesian RMST-based design compared with two HR-based methods—MYS-S (subgroup-specific HRs) and MYS-R (HRs from a regression model with subgroup covariates). Each simulation generated 1,000 replicated trials with 600 patients distributed across four biomarker subgroups. Control arm survival followed an exponential distribution with a median of 4.2 months. Experimental arm survival followed a piecewise exponential model allowing time-dependent hazard ratios after three months to emulate delayed or crossing effects. Censoring was applied at 30 months.

Two major factors were varied: (1) Subpopulation proportion patterns (equal, concentrated in middle subgroups, or decreasing); and (2) Clinical scenarios representing distinct treatment-effect dynamics—null (no effect), proportional hazards, delayed effect, and reversal of hazards. Each combination was analyzed independently (Table 1), and expected survival curves for each scenario are shown in Figure 1. The primary performance measure was the proportion of simulations correctly identifying truly sensitive subgroups (Subgroups 3 and 4). Incorrect classifications were categorized as none, only 4, 2–4, or all.

Table 1: Subpopulation proportion patterns and Clinical scenarios settings

			Subgroup			
			1	2	3	4
Subpopulation proportion patterns			φ_1	φ_2	φ_3	φ_4
	Equal		0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
	Higher in subgroups 2 & 3		0.15	0.35	0.35	0.15
	Decreasing		0.50	0.30	0.15	0.05
Clinical scenario			HR ₁	HR ₂	HR ₃	HR ₄
Null	HR ₁	Interval 1 (0~3)	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
	HR ₂	Interval 2 (3~30)	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
HR ₁ =HR ₂	HR ₁	Interval 1 (0~3)	1.0	1.0	0.7	0.5
	HR ₂	Interval 2 (3~30)	1.0	1.0	0.7	0.5
HR ₁ =1, HR ₂ <1	HR ₁	Interval 1 (0~3)	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
	HR ₂	Interval 2 (3~30)	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.3
HR ₁ >1, HR ₂ <1	HR ₁	Interval 1 (0~3)	1.0	1.0	1.7	2.0
	HR ₂	Interval 2 (3~30)	1.0	1.0	0.3	0.1

Figure 1: Expected survival curves under different clinical scenarios

Expected survival curves for the experimental (green, yellow, blue, and red lines) and control (black line) arms under four clinical scenarios. Panel (A) shows the null scenario with no treatment effect. Panel (B) depicts proportional hazards with a constant HR; Panel (C) illustrates a delayed treatment effect, where the benefit appears after 3 months; and Panel (D) represents a reversal of hazards, where early hazards favor the control arm but long-term survival favors the experimental arm. In Panels (B), (C), and (D), treatment is effective in subgroups 3 and 4.

3.2. Evaluation and comparative methods

The primary performance measure was the proportion of simulated trials that correctly identified the truly sensitive subgroups (Subgroups 3 and 4). This measure, denoted as P_{3-4} , represents the true positive rate of correct identification. Other outcomes were categorized as follows: P_{none} – no subgroup judged effective; P_4 – only Subgroup 4 judged effective; P_{2-4} – Subgroups 2–4 judged effective; and P_{all} – all subgroups judged effective. These metrics collectively describe both the accuracy and the degree of over- or under-classification of sensitive subpopulations.

To evaluate comparative performance, the proposed RMST-based Bayesian design was benchmarked against two existing HR-based Bayesian subgroup identification methods: MYS-S, which estimates subgroup-specific hazard ratios independently within each biomarker-defined subgroup; and MYS-R, which models a pooled hazard ratio using a regression framework that includes subgroup covariates. The comparison focused on the relative frequency of each classification outcome (P_{none} , P_4 , P_{3-4} , P_{2-4} , P_{all}) across the four clinical scenarios, highlighting the ability of each method to accurately detect treatment-sensitive subgroups under varying non-proportional hazard structures.

4. Results

4.1. Performance Across Clinical Scenarios

Simulation outcomes summarized in Table 2 show clear trends. Under the null scenario, all methods maintained high true-negative rates, indicating good type I error control. The proposed RMST-based approach was the most conservative, yielding the lowest false-positive frequency.

When the proportional hazards assumption held, performance across all methods was comparable, confirming that the RMST-based approach does not sacrifice efficiency when the PH assumption is valid. This equivalence demonstrates backward compatibility with conventional analyses.

In the delayed effect scenario, where the experimental treatment benefit emerged after approximately three months, the RMST-based design achieved markedly higher correct identification rates ($\approx 65\%$) than either HR-based alternative. Because HRs estimated early in follow-up underestimate delayed benefits, HR-based methods frequently failed to classify truly sensitive subgroups. The RMST-based model, in contrast, integrated the full survival experience over 30 months and successfully captured cumulative benefit.

The reversal of hazards scenario was the most challenging, with early harm followed by long-term benefit. Here, the RMST-based design achieved a correct identification rate of 71%, outperforming MYS-S (33.5%) and MYS-R (41.5%). These results reflect a critical advantage: RMST remains stable and interpretable even when hazards cross, whereas HR-based inference becomes unstable and misleading.

Table 2: Summary of simulation results across clinical scenarios

Three Bayesian subgroup identification methods were compared: RMST, the proposed design using the restricted mean survival time difference; MYS-S, based on subgroup-specific hazard ratios; and MYS-R, based on a regression model with subgroup covariates. Each column shows the proportion (%) of 1,000 simulated trials classified as: P_{none} (no subgroup effective), P_4 (only Subgroup 4), P_{3-4} (true sensitive subgroups correctly identified), P_{2-4} (Subgroups 2–4), and P_{all} (all subgroups effective). A higher P_{3-4} indicates greater accuracy.

Scenario	Subpopulation	Method	P_{none}	P_4	P_{3-4}	P_{2-4}	P_{all}
Null	Equal	RMST	0.937	0.010	0.010	0.021	0.022
		MYS-S	0.886	0.024	0.028	0.033	0.029
		MYS-R	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	Higher in subgroups 2 & 3	RMST	0.933	0.027	0.006	0.004	0.030
		MYS-S	0.842	0.050	0.019	0.015	0.074
		MYS-R	0.998	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.000
	Decreasing	RMST	0.876	0.069	0.035	0.018	0.002
		MYS-S	0.771	0.131	0.063	0.030	0.005
		MYS-R	0.987	0.010	0.003	0.000	0.000
$HR_1=HR_2$	Equal	RMST	0.000	0.098	0.859	0.021	0.022
		MYS-S	0.000	0.115	0.823	0.032	0.030
		MYS-R	0.000	0.107	0.868	0.017	0.008
	Higher in subgroups 2 & 3	RMST	0.000	0.041	0.925	0.004	0.030
		MYS-S	0.000	0.048	0.866	0.014	0.072
		MYS-R	0.001	0.047	0.938	0.008	0.006

HR ₁ =1, HR ₂ <1	Decreasing	RMST	0.022	0.178	0.780	0.018	0.002
		MYS-S	0.023	0.176	0.764	0.030	0.007
		MYS-R	0.046	0.160	0.778	0.014	0.002
	Equal	RMST	0.000	0.193	0.764	0.021	0.022
		MYS-S	0.007	0.273	0.658	0.031	0.031
		MYS-R	0.009	0.258	0.715	0.014	0.004
	Higher in subgroups 2 & 3	RMST	0.004	0.135	0.820	0.004	0.030
		MYS-S	0.018	0.194	0.700	0.013	0.075
		MYS-R	0.020	0.166	0.795	0.014	0.005
HR ₁ >1, HR ₂ <1	Decreasing	RMST	0.059	0.240	0.681	0.018	0.002
		MYS-S	0.001	0.268	0.597	0.028	0.006
		MYS-R	0.156	0.221	0.610	0.011	0.002
	Equal	RMST	0.002	0.245	0.710	0.021	0.022
		MYS-S	0.262	0.342	0.335	0.030	0.031
		MYS-R	0.169	0.407	0.415	0.007	0.002
	Higher in subgroups 2 & 3	RMST	0.010	0.169	0.787	0.004	0.030
		MYS-S	0.311	0.254	0.352	0.012	0.071
		MYS-R	0.270	0.291	0.434	0.003	0.002
Decreasing	RMST	0.071	0.254	0.655	0.018	0.002	
	MYS-S	0.393	0.248	0.323	0.029	0.007	
	MYS-R	0.320	0.250	0.419	0.008	0.003	

4.2. Sensitivity to Sample Size

Figure 2 presents the sensitivity analysis under the reversal-of-hazards scenario. The RMST-based method maintained stable performance across total sample sizes of 300–600 patients, with accuracy increasing gradually as sample size grew. Even at N=300, the design correctly identified sensitive subgroups in nearly 60% of simulations, while HR-based approaches dropped below 40%. This result highlights the sample-size robustness of the RMST-based design, an essential property for exploratory phase II trials where resources are limited.

Figure 2: Sensitivity of subgroup identification accuracy to total sample size. Correct subgroup classification results under the reversal of hazards scenario across total sample sizes of $N = 300, 400, 500,$ and 600 . Each stacked bar represents the proportion of 1,000 simulated trials classified into five outcome categories: blue = P_{none} (no subgroup judged effective), light blue = P_4 (only Subgroup 4 judged effective), yellow = P_{3-4} (true sensitive subgroups correctly identified), pink = P_{2-4} (Subgroups 2–4 judged effective), and red = P_{all} (all subgroups judged effective). The height of the yellow section indicates the correct identification rate.

5. Discussion

This study introduces a Bayesian subgroup identification design using RMST as a survival summary measure. The method extends existing HR-based frameworks to accommodate non-proportional hazards, a feature increasingly relevant in immuno-oncology and molecular-targeted therapy.

The key advantages of the proposed approach are threefold. First, clinical interpretability: RMST directly quantifies the absolute survival gain, offering a measure easily communicated to clinicians and regulators. Second, robustness to time-varying effects: the approach remains valid under delayed or crossing hazards, where HR-based inference often fails. Third, Bayesian adaptability: the posterior-probability criterion enables intuitive decision rules and straightforward sequential evaluation of subgroups.

Importantly, the framework can be adapted for adaptive or hierarchical extensions, such as dynamic borrowing across subgroups or interim analyses for early stopping. It can also accommodate continuous biomarkers through latent Gaussian process modeling, enabling smoother subgroup boundaries. Several considerations remain. The choice of the efficacy threshold (η) and posterior probability level (π) strongly influences operating characteristics and should be calibrated via simulation in collaboration with clinical experts. Additionally, the method assumes monotonicity of treatment effect with biomarker expression, which, although biologically plausible, may not always hold in practice. Future research should investigate partial-order or non-monotone extensions and explore integration with Bayesian hierarchical shrinkage priors to borrow strength across related subgroups.

Overall, the RMST-based Bayesian design provides a flexible, interpretable, and computationally feasible framework for identifying sensitive subpopulations in early-phase oncology trials. By accommodating complex survival dynamics, it offers a practical solution to the limitations of conventional HR-based approaches and aligns well with the goals of precision medicine.

Acknowledgements

The author expresses sincere gratitude to Professor Kyoji Furukawa of the Biostatistics Center, Kurume University, for his invaluable guidance, thoughtful advice, and continuous encouragement throughout the study.

References

- [1] Roychoudhury S, Anderson KM, Kay R, Saad ED, Ruberg SJ. Deviation from the proportional hazards assumption in randomized phase 3 clinical trials in oncology: Prevalence, associated factors, and implications. *Clin Cancer Res.* 2018;24(24):6305–6314.
- [2] Hernán MA. The hazards of hazard ratios. *Epidemiology.* 2010;21(1):13–15.
- [3] Chen TT. Statistical issues and challenges in immuno-oncology. *J Immunother Cancer.* 2013;1:18.
- [4] Chen TT. Statistical challenges in the design of late-stage cancer immunotherapy studies. *Cancer Immunol Res.* 2015;3(12):1292–1298.
- [5] Freidlin B, McShane LM, Korn EL. Randomized clinical trials with biomarkers: Design issues. *J Natl Cancer Inst.* 2010;102(3):152–160.
- [6] Mandrekar SJ, Sargent DJ. Clinical trial designs for predictive biomarker validation: One size does not fit all. *J Biopharm Stat.* 2009;19(3):530–542.
- [7] Simon R. Clinical trial designs for evaluating the medical utility of prognostic and predictive biomarkers in oncology. *PerMed.* 2010;7(1):33–47.
- [8] Morita S, Yamamoto H, Sugitani Y. Biomarker-based Bayesian randomized phase II clinical trial design to identify a sensitive patient subpopulation. *Stat Med.* 2014;33:4008–4016.
- [9] Sugitani Y, Morita S, Nakakura A, Yamamoto H. Biomarker-based Bayesian randomized clinical trial design for identifying a target population. *Stat Med.* 2023;42(16):2797–2810.
- [10] Borghaei H, Paz-Ares L, Horn L, Spigel DR, Steins M, Ready NE, et al. Nivolumab versus docetaxel in advanced nonsquamous non-small-cell lung cancer. *N Engl J Med.* 2015;373(17):1627–1639.
- [11] Horiguchi M, Hassett MJ, Uno H. How do the accrual pattern and follow-up duration affect the hazard ratio estimate when the proportional hazards assumption is violated? *Oncologist.* 2019;24(7):867–871.
- [12] Royston P, Parmar MKB. The use of restricted mean survival time to estimate the treatment effect in randomized clinical trials when the proportional hazards assumption is in doubt. *Stat Med.* 2011;30(19):2409–2421.
- [13] Pak K, Uno H, Kim DH, Tian L, Kane RC, Takeuchi M, et al. Interpretability of cancer clinical trial results using restricted mean survival time as an alternative to the hazard ratio. *JAMA Oncol.* 2017;3(12):1692–1696.
- [14] Royston P, Parmar MKB. Restricted mean survival time: An alternative to the hazard ratio for the design and analysis of randomized trials with a time-to-event outcome. *BMC Med Res Methodol.* 2013;13:152.
- [15] Uno H, Claggett B, Tian L, et al. Moving beyond the hazard ratio in quantifying the between-group difference in survival analysis. *J Clin Oncol.* 2014;32(22):2380–2385.
- [16] FDA-NIH Biomarker Working Group. BEST (Biomarkers, EndpointS, and other Tools) Resource. Silver Spring, MD: Food and Drug Administration; 2016.
- [17] Zhang C, Yin G. Bayesian nonparametric analysis of restricted mean survival time. *Biometrics.* 2023;79(2):1383–1396.